

PROBLEMS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PUBLIC PROCUREMENT AND DIRECTIONS FOR THEIR ELIMINATION

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Abstract

The article describes state procurement, its essence, theoretical foundations, and problems in the implementation of procurement. Also, the number of transactions on state purchases made through electronic commerce and the share of small business entities in them were analyzed. Based on the results of the analysis, suggestions for improving the implementation of public procurement were developed.

Key words: Government purchases, purchase, public customers, transaction, electronic transaction, small business.

As a component of the changes being carried out on the reform of public finance management in order to ensure the sustainable development of the economy of the new Uzbekistan, the fundamental reform of the organization of public procurement, the formation of the legal framework regulating it, the improvement of the efficiency of the use of public expenses, the saving of budget funds and the free competition between small business entities is an important means of development. From this point of view, the effective organization of the procurement mechanism for state needs mainly depends on the level of qualification and professional training of qualified specialists operating in the field. In developed countries, the government is directly responsible for training and improving the skills of public procurement personnel.

A systematic approach to public procurement management would be appropriate. Therefore, the process of planning the purchase of goods (work, services) for state needs, ensuring the transparency of the competitive environment in electronic sales creates a state procurement system[1]. Foreign economist A.Filippov[2] "divides state procurement into three types in terms of innovation orientation: - formalization of state procurement of "standard" goods (services) (cars, office equipment) based on standard selection criteria; - formalization of state procurement for goods (services) (industrial and medical equipment, architectural projects) with high technological and scientific capacity based on "complex" selection criteria; - state purchases based on the results of scientific research, in which the selection criteria are distinguished by the fact that they are of special importance.

V. Ovchinsky emphasizes that "determining the economic efficiency of providing the state's needs is related to the formation of the requirements of the state's customers. In this, first of all, it is important to justify the initial (maximum) prices for the delivery of orders in the planning of public procurement, and the customer plays the main role. In the second stage, the implementation of works for the fulfillment of contracts is of special importance, and the supplier will have the main role"[3], he emphasizes. The reforms implemented in the system of public procurement in terms of the wide introduction of information and communication technologies and the further expansion of opportunities for entrepreneurs to make electronic purchases have brought great results. In our country, the legal foundations of this mechanism have been created, and more than 30 regulatory and legal documents related to the field have been adopted and are being consistently implemented.

Particular attention is paid to the control over the purposeful and rational use of state budget funds and other centralized sources for the implementation of public procurement, the active involvement of small business entities in the process of public procurement, and the creation of favorable conditions for them in order for the procurement to be broad and convenient.

In connection with the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Procurement" by 2020, the participation of entrepreneurs in public procurement has become more active as a result of providing information to business entities, creating convenience for business entities in the field of public procurement, and simplifying the working mechanism for electronic procurement.

In 2022, the number of business entities participating in state procurement amounted to 58,701, of which 85.6 percent are small business entities. Analyzing the number of e-government procurement transactions and the share of small business entities in them, 347,038 transactions were concluded in 2017, of which 99.5 percent were implemented by small business entities (Table 1). The number of e-commerce transactions by 2022 reached 473,661 transactions, of which 98.8 percent were implemented by small business entities.

Table 1

The number of government procurement transactions carried out through e-commerce and the share of small business entities in them

Indicators	2017 y	2018 y	2019 y	2020 y	2021 y	2022 y
Number of transactions completed in electronic government procurement	347 038	470 285	301 230	419 758	490 677	473 661
Of these: the number of transactions completed by small businesses	345 456	467 825	299 047	417 239	487 998	468 071
Share in relation to the number of transactions (in percent)	99,5	99,5	99,3	99,4	99,5	98,8

Government purchases directly affect the formation of the country's gross domestic product. By consistently improving the state procurement system, their share in the gross domestic product is being increased. The analysis shows that in 2022, the share of purchases made by state customers in our country was 21.4% of the GDP. There are a number of problems in the implementation of public procurement in the country including:

1. **Insufficient information:** One of the main problems is insufficient information on public procurement. This may be due to the fact that information is not published on time or is published only from a narrow range of sources and does not have access to a wider audience. Information may be incomplete or unclear, making it difficult to understand the purchasing process.

2. **Corruption and Irregularities:** Informative estimation of public procurement also faces the problem of corruption and irregularities. Some customers may provide information only to certain suppliers in exchange for bribes or other benefits. Information may be altered or falsified, which may lead to incorrect decisions;

3. **System Imperfections:** Finally, the public procurement information system may be imperfect. For example, electronic platforms may not be sufficiently functional or meet international standards. Monitoring and control systems are ineffective and do not provide sufficient opportunities to prevent corruption and violations.

Studying these problems and developing recommendations for solving them is one of the important tasks of increasing the efficiency and transparency of the public procurement process in the Republic. These problems can have negative consequences for the state, public procurement participants, and

society as a whole. Therefore, it is very important to study these issues and develop recommendations to meet them. In order to improve the implementation of public procurement in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to implement the following measures:

- creation of a single database containing information on all public procurements, participants, terms, and costs;
- improvement of the procurement process monitoring and control system, including the introduction of more modern technologies and electronic systems;
- expansion of opportunities for the general public and specialized organizations to use information, which increases competition and transparency of the process.
- necessity to improve and simplify the process of electronic signing and approval of documents.

In general, improving the implementation of public procurement increases the efficiency and transparency of the use of budget expenditures in Uzbekistan and serves to meet the needs of society.

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